

Supplemental Material

CRB2 Depletion Induces YAP Signaling and Disrupts Mechanosensing in Podocytes

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Figure S1: *CRB2* colocalizes with TRPC6 in immortalized human podocytes. *CRB2* is expressed throughout the apical membrane of mature, immortalized human podocytes and demonstrates regional colocalization with the slit diaphragm protein TRPC6 (Inset). Scale bar, 25 μm .

Figure S2: *CRB2* staining in glomeruli bearing the p.Gly1036Alafs*43 truncating mutation.

Representative kidney biopsy images with CRB2 and Nephrin staining in a healthy human glomerulus (control), a patient with FSGS due to a pathogenic *TRPC6* mutation and a patient with biopsy proven FSGS bearing the pathogenic truncating p.Gly1036Alafs*43 mutation. The uniform distribution of podocyte CRB2 staining in the control is largely preserved but mildly irregular in the patient with the *TRPC6* mutation. Notably, in the patient with FSGS due to the truncating *CRB2* mutation, CRB2 staining is obliterated, consistent with the predicted effect of the mutation to prevent the transmembrane insertion of the protein. Scale bar, 20 μm .

Figure S3: Focal adhesion density is enhanced in *CRB2* KD podocytes.

Focal Adhesion Kinase (FAK) staining is used to identify focal adhesions by indirect immunofluorescence imaging in siScr and si*CRB2* podocytes (Insets). Although the number of focal adhesions per cell is similar in both lines, the focal adhesion density is greater in si*CRB2* podocytes due to their significantly reduced cell area as shown in Figure 2c of the main text. Scale bar, 25 μm .

Figure S4: Podocyte contractile forces are colocalized with paxillin expression in FAs at cell periphery.

a) Composite immunofluorescence images of the representing control (siScr) and CRB2 knockdown (siCRB2) podocytes. Shown are F-actin (detected by TRITC-phalloidin, green), paxillin (red) and nuclei (detected by DAPI, blue) of differentiated control and siCRB2 podocytes. **b)** Corresponding ERISM displacement and **c)** Fourier-filtered maps, with black lines denoting paxillin-rich area. Scale bars, 20 μm . F-actin, filamentous actin.

Figure S5: No reduction in cell contractility of *CRB2* KD podocytes upon treatment with verteporfin at high dose.

Mean indented volume (symbols), means (central lines) and \pm SD (boxes) of individual 12-day differentiated podocytes after 24 h of verteporfin treatment at two different concentrations in dark and in DMSO control, for *CRB2* knockdown (*siCRB2*) podocytes. Excessive cell death was observed for *siCRB2* podocytes treated with 5 μ M of verteporfin. All groups were treated with 0.2% of DMSO and $N \geq 6$. Groups were compared using two-tailed Student *t*-tests with non-equal variance, n.s.: no significance, *: $p \leq 0.05$, **: $p \leq 0.01$, ***: $p \leq 0.001$.